

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION. PART XI. THE PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDATION OF GLUCOSE BY METHYLENE BLUE WITH URANIC ACID SOL AS PHOTOSENSITISER.

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Uranic acid sol was prepared as described before (*vide* Part IX, p. 581).

The change in the concentration of methylene blue was followed spectrophotometrically. The graph (Fig. 1) was obtained by plotting different concentrations of methylene blue in presence of a certain concentration of uranic acid ($0.021M$) against $\log \tan \alpha - \log \tan \alpha'$ [α =angular displacement with dye of a particular strength in presence of uranic acid ($0.021M$) and α' =that with uranic acid ($0.021M$) at $\lambda=525\mu\mu$]. Uranic acid ($0.042-0.021M$) has little absorption at $525\mu\mu$. And moreover as the concentration of uranic acid was constant during the course of reaction, the presence of uranic acid did not affect the estimation of methylene blue by this method. When uranic acid was changed, a separate standard graph was obtained for each case.

No reduction was observed when a solution of methylene blue (Merck's chemically pure sample) alone was exposed to ultraviolet light ($366\mu\mu$). There was no reaction when a mixture of uranic acid and methylene blue and glucose (Kahlbaum's pure anhydrous sample) was exposed to ultraviolet light. A mixture of glucose, uranic acid and methylene blue does not react when kept in the dark for about 14 hours.

A large induction period was observed in the photochemical reaction.

R E S U L T S.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Methylene Blue.

TABLE I.

Temp. = 32°. Methylene blue = 0.000612 M. Glucose = 0.025 M. Uranic acid sol = 0.021 M. $*I_{\text{abs.}} = 1180$. d (thickness of the reaction cell) = 0.5 cm.

	Time.	Readings of spectro- photometer.	Concentration of M.B.	K (zero-molecular with respect to M.B.) $\times 10^{10}$
1.	0 mins.	65.0	0.000612 M	1
2.	45	63.0	0.000549	1.92 (from 2 and 3).
3.	60	58.1	0.000377	1.97 (from 3 and 4).
4.	75	52.5	0.000200	
				Mean 1.95

* I_{abs} = Intensity of absorbed radiation in ergs/cm²/sec. [M.B. denotes methylene blue].

Similar readings were taken with other concentrations of methylene blue and the results are given below. The zero-molecular velocity constant was expressed in terms of no. of g. mols of methylene blue transformed in 1 sec. in a unit cell.

TABLE II.

Glucose = 0.025 M. Uranic acid sol = 0.021 M.

Methylene blue $\times 10^{-4}$ (M)	...	7.46	7.35	6.12	5.75	4.90	4.28
K (zero-mol.) $\times 10^{10}$	...	1.98	2.02	1.95	1.88	2.00	1.92
Quantum efficiency (γ)	...	0.97	1.00	0.97	0.94	0.97	0.94

The zero-molecular velocity constant does not undergo any change with change in the concentration of methylene blue.

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose.

Temp. = 32°. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 1180$.

Me blue = 6.12×10^{-4} M.

Uranic acid sol = 0.021 M.

Glucose (M)	0.025	0.0125	0.0063
K (zero-mol.) $\times 10^{10}$	1.95	1.25	0.70
γ	0.97	0.62	0.34

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the concentration of uranic acid sol.

Temp. = 32°. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 1180$.

Glucose = 0.025 M

Me blue = 6.12×10^{-4} M.

Uranic acid sol (M)	0.042	0.021
K (zero-mol.) $\times 10^{10}$	2.17	1.95
γ	1.08	0.97

It is found that $1/K$ plotted against $1/\text{conc.}$ of glucose gives a straight line (Fig. 2).

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

The zero-molecular constant diminishes slightly as the concentration of uranic acid sol is diminished.

Effect of Varying the Temperature.—The temperature coefficient is very small being of the order of 1.05–1.15.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Radiation.

TABLE V.

Me blue = $6.12 \times 10^{-4}M$. Glucose = $0.025M$. sol. = $0.021M$. Temp. = 32° .

I_{abs}	...	...	K (zero-molecular) $\times 10^{10}$
1180	...	...	1.95
370	...	...	0.57

It will be seen from the above table that the velocity constants vary directly as the intensity of absorbed radiation.

The molecular extinction coefficient of uranic acid and methylene blue at 366μ were measured with the help of a Moll thermopile and a Moll Galvanometer. The results are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Absorbing substance.	Mol. ext. coeff. (366 μ).
Uranic acid sol	28
Methylene blue	2500

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.

In Table I, the intensity of total radiation (366 μ) absorbed by a solution of 0.5 cm. thick = 1180 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec. = 3.603×10^{-10} Einstein per sq. cm. per sec.

Now the part of the energy absorbed by uranic acid only is effective in bringing about the photochemical change and is approximately

$$= 3.603 \times 10^{-10} \times \frac{0.021 \times 28}{0.021 \times 28 + 6.12 \times 10^{-4} \times 0.25 \times 10^4}$$

$$= 1.015 \times 10^{-10} \text{ Einstein per sq. cm. per sec.,}$$

the mol. extinction coefficients of uranic acid and methylene blue being 28 and 2500 respectively.

Since the zero-molecular velocity constant K (expressed in terms of no. of g. mols transformed in 1 sec. in a unit cell (1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm. $\times$ 1 cm.) = 1.95×10^{-10} .

No. of g. mols transformed in 1 sec. in a cell (1 cm $\times$ 1 cm $\times$ 0.5 cm.) = 0.98×10^{-10} , the thickness of the reaction cell being 0.5 cm. Quantum efficiency of the process

$$= \frac{0.98 \times 10^{-10}}{1.015 \times 10^{-10}} = 0.97.$$

Quantum yield for other experiments were similarly calculated.

TABLE VII.

Dependence of the velocity of radiation on the state of polarisation.

Nature of light.	I_{abs}	K (zer.-omol.) with respect to Me blue.
Unpolarised	1180	1.95×10^{28}
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	220	0.367
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	220	0.350

It will be seen from the above table that the velocity constant is not much affected by the nature of the activating light.

D I S C U S S I O N .

The photochemical reaction between methylene blue and glucose with uranic acid sol as photosensitiser is characterised by great simplicity.

- (1) The reaction is zero-molecular with respect to methylene blue.
- (2) The velocity is proportional to the intensity of light absorbed,
- (3) and is practically independent of the concentration of uranic acid sol provided that the sol strength is such as to ensure complete absorption of incident radiation. The quantum efficiency is of the order of unity. The mechanism of reaction must necessarily be the following :—

Methylene blue even in very small concentrations forms as in the case with most dyestuffs, a saturated unimolecular layer on the sol surface. The excited elementary spaces of the uranic acid sol surface, produced by the absorption of a quantum of radiation, activates a molecule of methylene blue adsorbed on the surface. These activated molecules of methylene blue on the surface of the sol particle react with a molecule of reductant also adsorbed on the surface of the sol.

The velocity of reaction is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K \cdot \frac{I}{Nh\nu} \cdot C_s^a = K \quad \dots (i)$$

where C_s^a is the surface concentration of glucose.

According to Langmuir, $C_s^a = \frac{K_1 C_s^a}{1 + K_2 C_s^a}$... (ii)

where C_s^a is the concentration of glucose in solution.

